

FAILURE PROPERTIES OF TOUGHENED BISMALEIMIDE THERMOSETS FOLLOWED BY ATOMIC FORCE MICROSCOPY

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ABSTRACT

The effect of several thermoplastics and thermoplastics particles, on the crack behaviour of a typical bismaleimide resin has been investigated. Resin samples were elaborated with optimized conditions in order to control the resulting morphology in the thermoset matrix [1]. Double Cleavage Drilled Compression (DCDC) [2] specimens were used to initiate mode I crack propagation in brittle samples. Local behaviours around the crack tip (from 100 nm to 10 µm) were followed with Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM). This particular protocol allowed to follow micro-scale mechanisms for different kinds of toughening. These surface observations were completed with fracture surface investigations, which give information about the fracture behaviour through the thickness of the samples.

1 INTRODUCTION

Aeronautic structures use more and more composite materials to reduce the products weight, in order to improve performance and to limit their environmental impact. Polymer matrix composite materials represent today more than 50% of last generation civil aircrafts structure (A350, B787). Most of thermoset matrices are epoxies with service temperatures below 110°C for long time services. To further optimize the composite part ratio, it is now necessary to use those materials in structural parts exposed to higher temperatures.

During machining, manufacturing phases and lifetime, structural composites parts may be subjected to impacts and stresses cycles. This is why high performance composites require excellent damage tolerance properties.

Among high performance thermoset matrices, bismaleimides offer potential in service temperature up to at least 200°C. To improve such brittle materials' toughness, a common strategy is to blend the thermoset monomers with other polymers and fillers. Epoxy resins still stand for the majority of matrices used in aeronautic composite materials for structures. They have a long history of increasing performance through various strategies. First fillers to be used were elastomers and elastomeric particles, which provided enhanced toughness but at the cost of a loss in mechanical and thermal properties. Solubilized thermoplastics were first used to control the viscosity of resins, but in addition, an increase in toughness was observed. Consequently, many investigations have been carried out to better understand the relationship between polymer blends structures and mechanical properties [3]. This study is along the same lines, using bismaleimide resins instead of epoxies.

2 MATERIALS

2.1 Chemical reagents and polymers

The bismaleimide resin used is a blend of 1,1'-(Methylenedi-4,1-phenylene)bismaleimide (BMI) and 2,2'-Diallylbisphenol A (DBA) with a 1.14/1 molar ratio. The soluble thermoplastic is a polyether sulfone (PES). The insoluble thermoplastic is a polyamide-imide (PAI), with a powder size around 10 μm .

2.2 Blend preparation and sample curing

The liquid part of the resin (DBA) is heated up to the required temperature for dissolution of PES (120°C) or BMI (130°C). If a thermoplastic is to be added, the blend is stirred until complete dissolution for PES or homogeneous dispersion for PAI. The solid part of the resin (BMI) is then added and the blend is stirred until complete dissolution. When no PAI is added, the mixture is amber clear. If PAI is added, the final blend is opaque and the dissolution time for BMI is estimated on the basis of previous blends.

Moulded samples are cured 1h at 180°C, 2h at 200°C and 6h at 250°C. The resulting glass transition temperature is measured around 300°C by dynamic mechanical analysis. Morphologies are identified on polished samples by optical microscopy in reflection.

3 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

3.1 Double Cleavage Drilled Compression (DCDC)

DCDC was first used to study the crack behaviour in brittle materials such as glass [2,4,5]. By compressing a beam in which a hole has been drilled, the stress concentration generates a local transverse tension [6]. If conditions are met for a crack to propagate, this tension opens the crack. A perfectly centred hole would result into a mid-plane crack in a perfect mode I. Furthermore, this geometry allows to propagate cracks under highly stable conditions [4].

DCDC specimens (40x8x4 mm³) were cut in cured plates. A 2 mm diameter hole was then drilled in their centre through the thickness. The upper side was finally polished with grinding papers and diamond gels down to 1 μm . Samples were notched on each face by slow indentation of a triangular razor blade along the diameter of the hole, in the mid-plane axis. This defines pre-cracks from which cracks will propagate along the main axis of the specimen. Figure 1 displays the sample configurations during a DCDC experiment.

Figure 1: DCDC sample configurations. A) Drilled sample. B) Notched sample under compression. C) Cracked sample.

A DCDC test proceeds as follow. A notched specimen is placed, polished side up, in a precision loading cell. Compression is applied with a controlled displacement speed of 0.01 mm/min. When the

two cracks propagate from the notched edges of the hole, the loading is stopped and the compression displacement maintained constant for the whole remaining procedure.

This mechanical experiment exhibits a great potential when combined with observation devices. For instance, measuring the crack opening profile gives quantitative information yielding to the stress intensity factor [5]. Our study focuses on phenomena around the crack tip at micro-scale. After the crack fast propagation, the area around a crack tip on the external surface is observed with an atomic force microscope. Scanning parameters were optimized to obtain images as fast as possible, with a sufficient resolution with respect to the encountered phenomena.

Up to eight signals are recorded at the same time. Images presented here come from the height signal and from the deflection error signal (difference between the deflection and the setpoint). White and black arrows indicate the propagation direction.

3.2 Toughness

Compact tension specimens were machined following the requirements of the IGC 04.26.680 standard. The critical stress intensity factor for mode I fracture (K_{IC}) was measured following the requirements of this standard. The notched samples were submitted to tension until crack propagation occurs and then discharged to start a new charge-discharge cycle until the measured force is out of the sensor's range. K_{IC} is calculated from the force at failure, sample dimensions and the pre-crack length on each cycle.

3.3 Fractography

Fractured surfaces were coated with a thin layer of platinum and observed with a Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM). Secondary electron signals were used. A satisfying contrast between the thermoset matrix and the thermoplastic parts was achieved and a fair appreciation of topological features was possible. On compact tension samples, two kinds of areas are observed: the fast crack area corresponding to the crack propagation and the crack stop area where the crack front can be found between two cycles.

4 INFLUENCE OF MORPHOLOGIES ON TOUGHNESS

4.1 Phase separation in bismaleimide thermosets

Much attention was paid to investigations of bismaleimide and thermoplastic blends. Polyether sulfones [7,8], polyether imides [1,9,10] and polyesters [11,12] have been used, leading to morphologies ranging from thermoplastic particles and inclusions (at low thermoplastic content) to phase-inverted structures (at high thermoplastic content), with co-continuous morphologies in-between.

Phase separation occurs during the thermoset/thermoplastic blend because the polymerization reaction consumes good solvent molecules (monomers) and generates species with a decreased solubilisation force (oligomers, branched species...).

In our study, only PES is prone to generate such morphologies. PAI being insoluble, the blend remains a particle dispersion even after curing. Using different PES content, the possibility to obtain various morphologies was confirmed. With 4.8%wt of PES, small particles (1-2 μm) are visible (Figure 2A). Increasing the PES content up to 9.1%wt leads to bigger particles (2 to 5 μm , Figure 2B). Some localized phase-inverted globules (over 100 μm) also appear (not shown here). With 13%wt of PES, big globules are spread all over the sample surface in a continuous phase that contains particles up to 10 μm (Figure 2C). No co-continuous morphology was observed under our experimental range of compositions.

For the sake of simplicity only morphologies exhibiting mainly particles were selected. Local observations during cracking were expected to be easier to analyse with interactions between particles and the crack-tip. Better comparison is also expected with PAI specimens. In both cases, the selected

morphologies had characteristic sizes compatible with AFM observation's length scale. Furthermore, increasing the thermoplastic content too much leads to processing problems (highly viscous blend, impossibility to degas completely...) and a decrease of some properties (thermal properties, solvent resistance...).

Figure 2: optical microscopy images of bismaleimide/PES blend morphologies. A) PES 4.8% wt. B) PES 9.1% wt. C) PES 13% wt.

4.2 Toughness improvement

The effect of thermoplastics addition was evaluated through different classical mechanical characterizations. The K_{IC} of the neat cured resin is around $0.66 \text{ MPa/m}^{1/2}$, which is close to values from the literature. Only a limited effect of thermoplastic has been observed here. With PES, an improvement around 14% was measured for both 4.8% wt and 9.1% wt blends. This suggests that for a given thermoplastic, the morphology more than the content has an influence. With 6.5% wt of PAI, a better enhancement (around 18%) was measured. Some studies have achieved greater K_{IC} improvements, but those were not restrained to particles-only morphologies and mechanical properties were sometimes heavily impacted [13].

Figure 3: K_{IC} measurements for different bismaleimide/thermoplastic blends.

5 INTERACTIONS OF CRACK WITH MORPHOLOGIES

5.1 In situ surface observations

As mentioned above, DCDC experiments enable crack propagation in mode I under controlled conditions. After the fast propagation step, the crack tip velocity decreases while the sample relaxes. During this lower speed phase, it is possible to catch AFM images from the crack tip and to get visualisation of phenomena that occurs during propagation.

A first noticeable side-observation on blends with PES is that PES particles exhibit a phase-inverted morphology. Small nodules, densely packed inside thermoplastic particles, are visible (Figure 4). Several events have been observed.

Figure 4: AFM images (deflection error signal) of a crack tip passing through a PES structured particle. A) t_0 . B) $t_0 + 413$ min. C) $t_0 + 1102$ min. The propagation direction is marked by arrows.

Figure 4 shows a particle being cut by the crack at several stages. In this case, the crack is crossing the particle roughly through its middle. Very little crack deviation is observed here but the shape of the tip is altered when inside the particle, suggesting quite heavy local heterogeneity. Figure 5 is the 3D reconstruction corresponding to Figure 4C. Some kind of plateau is visible under the surface level of the cracked particle. The precise nature of this signal, coming from a height sensor, is difficult to establish. AFM height images are here visible as the convolution of the real surface and the shape of the AFM tip. Consequently, it can clearly be seen on Figure 5 that the walls of the crack are sloping to join a few micrometres under the surface. The resulting angle is characteristic from the scanning tip, the crack edges being, in fact, much more parallel. This shows how topological information can be altered with AFM when sharp height changes are encountered. Here a height drop between 500 nm and 1 μm under the surface mean plane is visible. Previous observations on neat resin samples and of crack tips out of particles did not reveal such topological features. It can be at least suggested that some underlying material is located beneath the thermoplastic particle. Many hypotheses can be drawn from this: stretched particle, partial breaking of the particle on surface weak points, fibrils, crack blunting... It was not possible to observe this phenomenon more accurately even with a better resolution or by changing the scanning angle. Underlying material can be seen during the whole crack propagation through the particle.

Figure 5: AFM 3D reconstruction (from height signal) of a crack tip piercing through a PES structured particle.

When the crack tip meets the particle near a vertex, it is similarly cut. Figure 6A shows what seems to be at first sight a crack deviation along the particle-matrix boundary. Letting propagation go on a little further leads to a double-headed crack (Figure 6B). The second crack tip appears along the natural prolongation of the crack path before meeting the particle, meaning that the crack recovers its original propagation direction. The deviated crack tip is due to the debonding of the particle from the matrix.

Figure 6: AFM images (deflection error signal) of a crack tip cutting through a PES particle near a vertex. A) t_0 . B) $t_0 + 29$ min. The propagation direction is marked by arrows.

Using the same method with blends containing PAI, leads to very different observations. PAI particles remain in their original shape so that they are much more irregular than those obtained by PES phase separation. PAI and matrix hardness seem to be nearly the same, leading to little contrast after polishing.

Figure 7: AFM images (height signal) of a crack bypassing a PAI particle. A) t_0 . B) $t_0 + 30$ min. C) $t_0 + 42$ min. D) $t_0 + 55$ min. The propagation direction is marked by arrows.

The most visible effect of PAI particles is the modification of the crack path (Figure 7A). In most observations, the crack bypasses particles, generating kinks and curvature. Once the crack circles half of a particle, no propagation is observed at first (Figure 7A and B). In this “stationary” state, the crack tip direction is nearly orthogonal to the global propagation direction. This phase ends with the crack starting over along the main propagation direction (Figure 7C and D), which means a nearly 90° angle within the crack path.

Another phenomenon was encountered less frequently. The crack on Figure 8 changes from quite smooth edges to very a distorted tip. Examining cautiously the deflection error images (Figure 8B and C), it is possible to see some discontinuities in the polishing lines. These would correspond to a PAI particle, which estimated edge is drawn on Figure 8C. The crack tip distortion appears to be due to the presence of that particle, which does not deviate the crack as showed above, but which is being cut.

All these observations rely on surface investigations. It can be easily understood that it would stand for the visualisation of the propagation crack “from above”. The imaged plan is orthogonal to the crack plan. Surface observation may vary a lot from what happens in the core material, because it remains a free edge, because of surface preparation and because of out of plane deformation. To compare surface phenomena with volume behaviour, rupture surface on *post mortem* samples were investigated.

Figure 8: AFM images of a crack tip passing through a PAI particle. A) height signal. B) deflection error signal. C) deflection error signal with an estimation of the particle boundaries. The propagation direction is marked by arrows.

5.2 SEM fractography

Compact tension samples containing PES particles exhibit two kinds of fracture surface. The propagation area is very smooth with particles neatly cut (Figure 9A). This propagation mode is not representative of DCDC experiments. The crack stop area exhibits much more features that can be compared to AFM observations during DCDC experiments (Figure 9B).

Figure 9: SEM crack surface images of samples containing PES particles. A) fast crack area. B) crack stop area. The propagation direction is marked by arrows.

The first striking observation is the presence of oriented decohesion between PES particles and the BMI matrix (Figure 10). For partially separated particles, the broken surface is mainly located on the opposite side of the crack front contact point with the particle. For complete decohesion, the gap is larger on that same side. This has to be compared to the phenomenon described on Figure 6, where a secondary crack tip propagates along the particle's boundary, leading to a localised decohesion.

Figure 10: SEM crack surface images. Crack stop area in a blend containing PES particles. The propagation direction is marked by arrows.

Looking closely to PES particles brings two new pieces of information (Figure 11). First, small fibrils with a 20 nm thickness are visible in the particle/matrix decohesion gap. It was not possible to obtain similar observations with AFM, due to spatial resolution and the fact that the corresponding zone on the surface of a DCDC sample is very small. Second, the surface of the broken particles is highly distorted with out of plane tubular objects and porosity. This suggests a high deformation of the particle, with stretching and cavitation. This is supported by the underlying material described on Figure 5.

Apparent porosity could also be explained by the presence of voids inside the particles. By comparison, particles in fast propagation areas are neatly cut and their surface is quite smooth and the small cavities would correspond to the removal of thermoset inclusions. The tubular objects are not elongated out of the plane (Figure 9A). This tends to confirm that in crack stop area, particles are subjected to stretching and that the observed porosity is the result of cavitation (void creation) with a loss of thermoset inclusions more than an intrinsic void content.

Figure 11: SEM crack surface images. PES particles details in the crack stop area. The propagation direction is marked by arrows.

With PAI particles, crack surfaces appear to be much more distorted (Figure 12) with traces of particles removal. This confirms what was observed with cracks bypassing particles (Figure 7).

Figure 12: SEM crack surface image of a crack stop area in a blend containing PAI particles. The propagation direction is marked by the arrow.

Very specific fractographic features are visible. Figure 13 displays a crack stop line drawing an arc between two PAI particles (red arrows). This suggests a very well-known phenomenon: crack pinning. In this scenario, the crack front is locally delayed around particles, whereas it propagates in the particle-free areas. This has to be compared to the crack tip being “trapped” after bypassing a particle (Figure 7).

Figure 13: SEM crack surface image from a DCDC sample containing PAI particles. The propagation direction is marked by the arrow.

Finally, some cut PAI particles are recognized with a porous aspect compared to bypassed particles. Figure 14 shows such a cut particle. On the lower corners two uncut particles are visible (red arrows). The surface aspect is smoother, without any porosity.

Figure 14: SEM image of a cut PAI particle.

6 CONCLUSION

A new method to observe crack propagation in heterogeneous brittle materials has been introduced here. DCDC geometry allows a satisfying control over mode I crack propagation and AFM imaging enables local observation of crack phenomena. These phenomena have been showed consistent with classical SEM fractography. Furthermore, SEM fractography confirms that local processes on the surface of DCDC samples seem to be representative of what happens through the thickness. On the other hand, because AFM imaging is here a time-resolved observation method, better comprehension of the formation of the fractographic features can be achieved.

These methods are also a tool for the selection of interesting complex matrices with respect to the encountered crack behaviours. Here PAI toughening is more efficient than PES toughening, leading to the conclusion that in this particular case, creating distorted paths for the crack is more effective than dissipation through deformation of particles.

Many improvements are still to achieve, especially on sample design for a better control on propagation in pure mode I. This is also a critical point for composite samples, which are highly heterogeneous at our observation scale.

Finally, promising information is still to be drawn out of AFM images sequences, for instance with digital image correlation to measure the local strain fields.

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REFERENCES

- [1] E. Martuscelli, P. Musto, G. Ragosta M. Abbate, "Toughened thermosetting bismaleimides: molecular structure, morphology and mechanical properties," *Die Angewandte Makromolekulare Chemie*, vol. 246, pp. 23-48, 1997.

- [2] C. Janssen, "Specimen for fracture mechanics studies on glass," in *10th International Congress on Glass*, Tokyo, 1974.
- [3] J.C. Seferis B.S. Hayes, "Modification of thermosetting resins and composites through reformed polymer particles: a review," *Polymer Composites*, vol. 22, pp. 451-467, 2001.
- [4] W.L. Smith, E.P. Chen T.A. Michalske, "Stress intensity calibration for the double cleavage drilled compression specimen," *Eng. Frac. Mech.*, vol. 45, pp. 637-642, 1993.
- [5] L. Ponson, A. Grimaldi, M. George, G. Prevot, M. Ciccotti G. Pallares, "Crack opening profile in DCDC specimen," *Int. J. Fract.*, vol. 156, pp. 11-20, 2009.
- [6] C.E. Inglis, "Stresses in a plate due to the presence of cracks and sharp corners," *Trans. Inst. Nav. Archit.*, vol. 55, pp. 219-230, 1913.
- [7] Y.F. Yu, S.J. Li X.Y. Liu, "Viscoelastic phase separation in polyethersulfone modified bismaleimide resin," *Eur. Polym. J.*, vol. 42, pp. 835-842, 2006.
- [8] G.Z. Zhan, Z.W. Han, S.J. Li, Y.F. Yu X.Y. Liu, "Phase Morphology and Mechanical Properties of a Poly(ether sulfone)-Modified Bismaleimide Resin," *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, vol. 106, pp. 77-83, 2007.
- [9] J. Cui, X. Tang, Y. Ding, S. Li, J. Wang, Q. Zhao, X. Hua, X. Cai J. Jin, "On polyetherimide modified bismaleimide resins, 1 Effect of the chemical backbone of polyetherimide," *Macromol. Chem. Phys.*, vol. 200, pp. 1956-1960, 1999.
- [10] J. Cui, X. Tang, S. Li, J. Wang, Q. Zhao, X. Hua, X. Cai J. Jin, "Polyetherimide-Modified Bismaleimide Resins. II. Effect of Polyetherimide Content," *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, vol. 81, pp. 350-358, 2001.
- [11] H. Shiono, W. Fukuda, M. Tomoi T. Iijima, "Toughening of Bismaleimide Resin by Modification with Poly(ethylene phthalate) and Poly(ethylene phthalate-co-ethylene isophthalate)," *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, vol. 65, pp. 1349-1357, 1997.
- [12] N. Yuasa, M. Tomoi T. Iijima, "Modification of Three-Component Bismaleimide Resin by Poly(phthaloyl diphenyl ether) and Related Copolymers," *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, vol. 82, pp. 2991-3000, 2001.
- [13] N. Hayashi, T. Oyama, M. Tomoi T. Iijima, "Modification of bismaleimide resin by soluble poly(ester imide) containing trimellitimide moieties," *Polym. Int.*, vol. 53, pp. 1417-1425, 2004.